

#220 Analysis of unfolding failure in unidirectional and cross-ply CFRP curved laminates: Numerical and Experimental Study

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Unfolding Failure

Composites

Phase field

Abstract The delamination experienced by curved composite laminates when they are loaded under bending moments is termed unfolding failure. This failure is characterized by the interlaminar tensile strength (ILTS) and is generally obtained by the four-point bending test when applied to a curved unidirectional laminate with plies oriented at 0° . When the same test is applied to laminates with different ply orientations, the specimens fail at a load significantly lower than the predicted value. This reduction in load has been explained by the concept of induced unfolding, where the damage is initiated by intralaminar transverse cracks and further propagates as delamination in the presence of high interlaminar stresses. The present study focuses on understanding the failure mechanisms in unidirectional and cross-ply curved laminates.

Unidirectional curved laminates fail by pure interlaminar delamination, and this delamination is modelled using Abaqus cohesive elements at the $0^\circ/0^\circ$ interfaces. Since delamination propagation is very unstable and leads to convergence issues, a control algorithm is used to capture those instabilities and obtain a stable post-damage behavior.

Cross-ply layup configurations, defined and tested to illustrate the induced unfolding failure, exhibit multiple transverse cracks in weaker plies after failure. In order to show that failure in these configurations is initiated by matrix-dominated intralaminar damages, the phase field variational approach in terms of the UMAT/HETVAL subroutine is used. To show the interaction between intralaminar and interlaminar failure modes, models combining phase field elements with interfacial cohesive elements are used.

Finally, the reliability of the mentioned approaches is examined by correlating the numerical and experimental results for both configurations.